

Ethnopharmacological uses of animals in districts Muzaffarabad, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

Using faun based byproducts in folklore medicine is a centuries-old human activity that is still practiced in many parts of the world today. This study investigates the use of body parts of animals in folk-therapy by the people of Muzaffarabad. Individual and group interviews were conducted from 2019 to 2020 to collect data. The ethnopharmacological applications of 12 animals' species were reported. These applications utilized meat, skin, venom, whole body, fat and egg used to treat various diseases like back bone pain, bronchitis, cancer, joint pain, male potency, osteoporosis, paralysis, Parkinson's disease, skin disease and weakness. These findings provide important baseline data for the protection of wildlife variety in Muzaffarabad. Screening these animals for medicinally active compounds might aid in the creation of novel animal-based medications.

Keywords: Zotherapy, fauna, Folklore, Kashmir, Communities

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INTRODUCTION

Ethnopharmacology is the study of traditional uses of medicines and zotherapy is the study of traditional uses of animal in folk medicines (Aloufi and Eid, 2016; Adil *et al.*, 2019; Kanwal *et al.*, 2019; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020; Noor and Haider, 2020; Shoukat *et al.*, 2020; Ahmad *et al.*, 2021). The consumption of animals with therapeutic characteristics is still a popular practice across the entire planet. Zotherapy methods and substances are used in both traditional and nanotechnology to cure various illnesses (Svanberg and Locker, 2020; Akhtar, 2021; Nazir, 2021; Prakash and Verma, 2021; Habib, 2022; Manzoor and Safeer, 2022; Rahman *et al.*, 2022).

Zoonotic illnesses are infectious diseases that could be transmitted from animal to a person. Zoonotic illnesses have resulted in a number of important worldwide health of human i.e. malaria, avian flu, swine flu, yellow fever, SARS, MERS, West Nile virus, and so on, culminated in the present coronavirus pandemic catastrophe (Altaf, 2020; Adil, 2021; Altaf *et al.*, 2021b; Bilal *et al.*, 2021). Because various infections i.e. flue, fever and etc. have distinct modes of transmission, the danger of zoonotic illnesses varies depending on the faunal species with whom humans interact and the period and nature of interaction (Kruse *et al.*, 2004; Van Vliet *et al.*, 2017).

Anthropogenic impacts on forest landscape are multifaceted. Several local societies have long supported modes of existence i.e. generally balanced in terms of resource maintenance. On the alternative hand, capitalist forces, along with a theoretical nature-culture split pushed by the worldwide extend of colonial, have cause in extractivist methods to reserve usage that endanger the pliability of the many of landscapes (Altaf, 2016; Altaf *et al.*, 2017; Altaf *et al.*, 2018; Svanberg and Locker, 2020; Rahman *et al.*, 2022; Iqbal *et al.*, 2023). Knowing the maintenance of systems of bioculture requires ethnozoological study. Cultural uses of species of animals may encourage beliefs and attitudes that assist in the protection of wildlife; however, if they are practiced in an untenable way, or are prejudiced by industrialization or other economic and political issues, they might have bad effects on threatened species. The usage of animal species by native societies in folk-therapy and for traditional usages must be assessed in associatio to other issues like climatic as well as ecosystem modification (Alves, 2012; Alves *et al.*, 2018). There is a worldwide necessity discover novel approaches to cope with the current disaster of species extinction (Boivin *et al.*, 2016). Ethnobiology, on the other hand, provides critical insights into local community practices, permitting maintenance struggles to successfully engage with reserve stewards to improve the general reliability of biodiversity communities (Saunders, 2003; Dickman, 2010). The research on the therapeutic usages of wildlife by Muzaffarabad people is part of a wider study to examine how wildlife is used by indigenous communities throughout Pakistan (Aslam and Faiz, 2020; Ijaz *et al.*, 2020; Mughal *et al.*, 2020; Altaf *et al.*, 2021a; Ijaz and Faiz, 2021; Ijaz and Iftikhar, 2021; Saleem *et al.*, 2021; Ammatussalm, 2022; Faiz *et al.*, 2022; Saeed *et al.*, 2022; Umair *et al.*, 2022).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

Muzaffarabad is the highest populated city of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. It is located at the junction of the “Jhelum” as well as “Neelum” rivers. The district is present on the west by “Khyber Pakhtunkhwa”, on the north by the Neelum, and on the eastern side by the Indian-occupied Baramulla and Kupwara districts (Figure 1). It is situated in Himalayan mountain region (Khan *et al.*, 2018; Altaf *et al.*, 2022).

DATA COLLECTION

Data were collected from 2019 to 2020. The approval was taken from “Department of Zoology, Women's University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Bagh-Pakistan”, before commencing fieldwork. To document the ethnomedicinal usage of animals, interviews were used. Data were collected from 100 respondents (Figure 1). Informers were preferred based on their rudimentary understanding of wild animal folk medicine. For herptiles i.e. “*Amphibian and Reptiles of Pakistan*” (Khan, 2006), for birds i.e. “*Birds of Pakistan*” (Roberts, 1991, 1992) and for mammals i.e. “*Mammals of Pakistan*” (Roberts, 2005a, b) field guides and/or books were used to verify, observation and classification of species.

DATA ANALYSIS

Chord diagram is designed with the help of R program. Data was analyzed with the help of FC (Frequency of Citation) and RFC (Relative Frequency of Citation).

Figure 1: Map of Muzaffarabad (Khan *et al.*, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data were obtained from 79 males and 21 women in Muzaffarabad area. Because most women are housewives and avoid meeting strangers, more men were chosen for interviews (Figure). Because the majority of people live in rural regions, we obtained the majority of the data from rural areas and the remainder from urban areas. The informants work in a variety of vocations, including government employers, teachers, students, farmers, merchants, and residents in the research region. The majority of the informants were educated, while the remaining were illiterate (Figure).

The ethnopharmacological applications of 12 animals' species were reported (Table 1). These applications utilized meat, skin, venom, whole body, fat and egg used to treat various diseases like back bone pain, bronchitis, cancer, joint pain, male potency, osteoporosis, paralysis, Parkinson's disease, skin disease and weakness (Figure 3), mode of application is topical and oral to treat diseases (Figure 4, 5). During research documented that the highest RFC was reported in Common Quail (*Coturnix coturnix*) and followed by Black Francolin (*Francolinus francolinus*), Himalayan black bear (*Ursus thibetanus*), Himalayan toad (*Bufo himalayanus*) and Common leopard, *Panthera pardus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Figure 2: Respondents of study area.

Most species of animals have been shown to be frequent in use. Maximum relative significance levels may indicate that animals are easily accessible and affordable (Umair *et al.*, 2019). Ethnozoologists discovered that lipids are utilized to treat nerve problems, joints issues and ageing related problems (Breteler, 2000; Haag, 2003). Organic and inorganic compounds are present in meat (Keeton and Eddy, 2004; Hui, 2012), and its composition is varies in different ecosystems and species (Cheung and Mehta, 2015). Bones include upto “95 percent” elastic protein and collagen fibers, alongwith “calcium” and “phosphate” minerals, which help to prevent bone fractures (Hall, 2011). Excellent protein, minerals, vitamins are present in eggs and other compounds and components for people of all ages. Apart for vitamin C, it is a major source of important nutrients for humans. Eggs are an incredibly tasty and healthful item that can be employed in a variety of recipes (Tariq, 2020). Venom is used to treat various diseases like cancer, and also used to prepare antivenom (Altaf and Faiz, 2021; Daghestani *et al.*, 2021; Salmanzadeh Zekhesh and Mohammadpour Donighi, 2021; Jimenez-Canale *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 3: Body parts used in tradition medicines.

Figure 4: (a) Modes of used of body parts in tradition medicine, (b) Body parts used against diseases.

CONCLUSIONS

Ethnopharmacological usages of the study area's rich fauna have never been described.

- These results demonstrated that native societies have strong bonds with wild fauna in their surroundings and use them to treat a range of diseases in the primary health care system.
- In order to generate novel animal-based pharmaceutical products wild fauna with high therapeutic advantages should be explored further in vitro and/or in vivo activators.

Table 1: Ethnopharmacological uses of animals in study area.

Sr.	Common name	Scientific name	Parts used	Application	Diseases	FC	RFC
Herptiles							
1	Himalayan toad	<i>Bufo himalayanus</i> (Gunther, 1864)	Skin	Topical	Joint pain	11	0.06
2	Bengal monitor	<i>Varanus bengalensis</i> (Daudin, 1802)	Fat	Topical	Weakness, joint pain	9	0.05
3	Red spotted diadem snake	<i>Spalerosophis diadema</i> (Schelegel, 1837)	Venom	Topical	Cancer	6	0.03
4	Oriental Garden Lizard	<i>Calotes versicolor</i> (Daudin, 1802)	Fat	Topical	Skin disease, joint pain	4	0.02
5	Fat tail gecko	<i>Eublepharis macularius</i> (Blyth, 1854)	Skin	Topical	Cancer, back bone problem	5	0.03
6	Rat snake	<i>Ptyas mucosus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Whole body	Topical	Cancer, weakness	3	0.02
Mammals							
7	Common leopard	<i>Panthera pardus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Fat	Topical	Paralysis, joint pain	11	0.06

8	Himalayan black bear	<i>Ursus thibetanus</i> (G. Cuvier, 1823)	Fat	Topical	Paralysis	17	0.10
9	Alpine Musk	<i>Moschus chrysogaster</i> (Hodgson1839)	Meat	Oral	Male potency	8	0.05
Birds							
10	Common Quail	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	Meat	Oral	Joint pain, back bone pain and paralysis	34	0.19
11	Rock Pigeon	<i>Columba livia</i> (Gmelin, 1789)	Meat, Egg	Oral	Paralysis, Parkinson's disease	56	0.32
12	Black Francolin	<i>Francolinus francolinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1766)	Meat	Oral	Osteoporosis and bronchitis	12	0.07

Note: FC means “Frequency of Citation”, RFC means “Relative Frequency of Citation”.

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